

CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT THROUGH YOUTH INVOLVEMENT

PROVIDING FEEDBACK ON FIRST
RELEASE OF THE GREENSCENT
COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK

WORKSHOP IN THE GREENSCENT
YOUTH ASSEMBLIES, NOVEMBER 2022

THE REPORT INCLUDES

INTRODUCTION.....	2
YOUTH INVOLVEMENT	2
THE FEEDBACK PROCESS.....	3
METHODOLOGY	4
FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE AREAS: THE OCTAGON	5
FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORKS' WEBPAGE.....	6
FURTHER PROCESS & YOUTH REFLECTIONS.....	7
APPENDIX - FULL FEEDBACK REPORT.....	9

INTRODUCTION

Citizen Participation is a key component of the GreenSCENT project, to ensure relevant content of the pilots and the corresponding curriculum. In the development of a change-making and relevant green Curriculum, it is essential to involve and collaborate with young European students, who are the end users of the educational programs developed in the GreenSCENT project.

Thus, four Youth Assemblies (YAs) with a total of 56 young people (14 in each) have been established to discuss, evaluate, and give feedback to elements in the GreenSCENT project, including the GreenSCENT Competence Framework. The participants are aged between 15 and 25 (ranging from primary school to higher education) and come from 7 of the partnering countries: Italy, Romania, Greece, Netherlands, Denmark, Spain, and Serbia.

YOUTH INVOLVEMENT

The Youth Assemblies convened on November 17th and 18th 2022 in a 3-hour workshop meeting to give valuable feedback and help co-create the GreenComp with the experts from UNINETTUNO. DBT facilitated and organized the workshop, while UNINETTUNO presented the GreenSCENT Competence Framework and helped the participants with clarifying questions during the meeting.

The Youth Assembly acted as an expert panel by providing guidance, innovative ideas, and constructive feedback on the first version of the GreenComp. This was the first step in starting a bottom-up approach to improve and increase clarity of the Competence Framework. The workshop was divided into the following sections:

THE FEEDBACK PROCESS

1

The participants reflected on their everyday contribution to the green transition, and their abilities to achieve political influence. They discussed what competences or green skills they need to achieve their desires for participation and contribution.

2

The participants shared their thoughts on the competences in the GreenSCENT Compete Framework described in the Octagon. They worked in groups of interest, and each participant shared their feedback on two different competences. All competences received feedback in the process.

3

The participants individually explored the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page and answered yes/no questions, guiding them to get an overview of the framework.

4

The participants explored the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page in groups with 4-5 participants. They answered questions regarding the framework, which encouraged the participants to share ideas, questions, and constructive feedback.

METHODOLOGY

The questions in the workshop were close to the text, content-relevant and oriented towards the overall expressions. Thus, the questions ensured feedback on multiple levels of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework. The feedback from the meeting was gathered in Mural during the workshop and is analysed and summarized in this report.

DBT uses qualitative methods in obtaining and analysing the feedback. Thus, the data/feedback is collected by open dialogue, as the participants share their thoughts guided by open questions. The qualitative approach offers opportunities to gain knowledge about the Competence Framework that are difficult to quantify and measure with numbers, e.g., the first impression and the understanding of the competencies.

The feedback from the workshop was collected and themed, which provided varied and detailed feedback. The feedback from the workshop is briefly presented below. In addition, DBT has prepared a detailed analysis for UNINETTUNO.

Young participants are providing their consideration about the Knowledge Graph on the Mural board during the co-design workshop with the Youth Design Assembly.

FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE AREAS PRESENTED AS AN OCTAGON

The participants reflected on the competence areas presented in the octagon and generally found the competences in the GreenSCENT Competence Framework important and relevant. The participants primarily gave feedback on their general impression, suggested new competencies, and gave their perspective on the most important competencies in the competence areas.

The participants presented a lot of ideas, questions, and feedback regarding each of the competence areas. The most important points from the collected feedback are briefly presented in the table below:

Summarization: Feedback on the competence areas in the GreenSCENT Competence Framework
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The participants find the competencies relevant and important.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The participants find some competencies too general. This is often competencies named as system thinking, critical thinking and general competencies. Some participants suggest that they need some context to ensure understanding, while others suggest that the competencies should be considered as general competencies to all competence areas.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The participants suggest new competencies, new perspectives and ask questions regarding the competence areas. These perspectives should be taken into consideration in the formulation and expansion of the competencies in each competence area.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The participants suggest that some of the competencies could be simpler described. These competencies are described in detail in the full analysis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The participants suggest that the Octagon is implemented in the Green Comp web page, to give an overview over the competencies.

FEEDBACK ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORKS' WEBPAGE - APPEARANCE AND USABILITY

The participants have a constructive approach to the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page. They think it is a relevant tool, but encourages organization, simplification, and clarification. They have proposed many ideas to ensure this. The most important points, ideas and suggestions are briefly presented in the table below:

Summarization: Feedback on the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' webpage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants encourage to move the 'start here' page to the top of the content list, or to automatically make it the start page on the web page.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants propose to make a drop menu, to strengthen the organisation and overlook of the GreenComp.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants propose more space between the competences in the mind map, and that they should be able to read the competences in the mind map.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants propose colours, everyday examples, and pictures to make the GreenComp easier to understand and navigate.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants ask for more introductions and simpler language, to make sure that the users will understand the GreenComp and how to use it.

FURTHER PROCESS & YOUTH REFLECTIONS

OTHER REFLECTIONS REGARDING THE GREENSCENT PROJECT IN GENERAL

During the meeting, the participants reflected on which skills they need to learn, to gain political influence or to make a difference in their day-to-day lives. The participants described 4 competences or needs for knowledge that can be incorporated in the GreenComp or in the pilots developed in the GreenSCENT project.

The youth wish to obtain convincing knowledge about the green transition, to be able to change other peoples' minds about the importance of the green transition.

The youth want to learn how to make a green change in day-to-day life.

The youth need competencies to use social media as a way of spreading the word of the green transition.

The youth want to learn how to use activism, organize protests, and demonstrations to gain political influence.

FURTHER CO-CREATION ON THE GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK

The GreenSCENT Competence Framework was presented as a first draft to the YA (Youth Assembly). The YA has given feedback, ideas of improvement and has contributed with their first-hand impressions. This is the first step in a bottom-up approach to achieve a useful and simple tool to teach green competencies to students on different educational levels in the EU. When the GreenSCENT Competence Framework is further developed, the YA will be presented to it on the in-person meetings in September and October, and once again in January 2024. They will be presented with the changes made, based on their feedback. The YA will in this meeting get a change to give their final feedback to the tool/product.

A special thanks to all participants in the GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies for engaging in developing ideas and sharing reflections and insights on the green apps.

APPENDIX

In addition to this report, you can read the full combined feedback report with all statements, reflections and ratings from the four feedback workshops below.

YOUTH ASSEMBLY REPORT: Full combined feedback report of the empirical data on the GreenSCENT Competence Framework

The GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies convened on November 17th and 18th 2022 in a 3-hour workshop meeting, to give valuable feedback and help co-create the GreenSCENT Competence Framework with the experts from UNINETTUNO.

DBT facilitated and organized the workshop, while UNINETTUNO presented the Competence Framework and helped the participants with clarifying questions during the meeting. The workshop was divided into several sections described below.

The Youth Assembly acted as an expert panel by providing guidance, innovative ideas, and constructive feedback on the first version of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework, presented both as the Octagon (s. 26) and the Obsidian web page. This is the full analysis of the feedback given on the workshop.

Part 1: Green Skills

During the meeting, participants reflected on their everyday contribution to the green transition, and their abilities to achieve political influence. They reflected on which skills they need to learn, to gain political influence or to make a difference in their day-to-day lives. The participants described 4 competences or needs for knowledge, that can be incorporated in the GreenSCENT Competence Framework or in the pilots developed in the GreenSCENT project.

The answers suggest that partners in the GreenSCENT project need to consider if these 4 subjects are covered in the competence framework or in the learning programs in general:

1. The youth wish to obtain convincing knowledge about the green transition, to be able to change other peoples' minds about the importance of the green transition.
2. The youth want to learn how to make a green change in day-to-day life.
3. The youth need competencies to use social media as a way of spreading the word of the green transition
4. The youth want to learn how to use activism, organize protests, and demonstrations to gain political influence.

Part 2: The GreenSCENT Competence areas (The Octagon)

The participants shared their thoughts on the competencies described in the Octagon. They worked in groups of interest, and each participant shared their feedback on two different competencies. All competencies received feedback in the process.

SMART MOBILITY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The participants find the competencies relevant.- They are critical of the coherence between headline and competencies.- They point out that the competencies should be formulated in a way that relates them directly to mobility or transportation. Or that the headline is altered.- The participants find 1.1 and 1.2 broad and state that they can be used in all competencies.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Conscious use of transport (walk if possible)- Green energy and life quality; why it is important to have smart mobility.

	- Consequences on urban communities without access to smart mobility
Questions	- They are unsure about what 'critical thinking,' 'Equity,' 'Monitoring and learning' and 'exploiting the opportunities' means in this context.

BIODIVERSITY	
General impression	- The participants find the competencies relevant and important to learn, but ask for easier/more intuitive words
Proposed competencies	- Water Flora - Water fauna - How to slow down extinction
Most important competencies	- The participants especially find competencies 4.2 and 2.1 important to learn.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY	
General impression	- The participants find the competencies relevant and important. - The participants find Circular economy particularly important in the green transition and see it as a solution to many of the other competency areas. - 5.5 was difficult to understand to some of the participants
Proposed competencies	- The importance of digital tools in the CE - Energy coming from natural resources - Promotion of the local products to increase the local economy - Planned obsolescence - Shift away from the take-make-waste - Examples from other countries/cities which successfully implemented a circular economy
Most important competencies	- The participants especially find these competencies important to learn: 1.4, 1.5, 4,2.
Questions	- What is the new business model? Any exact model?

ZERO POLLUTION	
General impression	- The participants find the competencies relevant and important to learn but ask for easier/more intuitive words. - The participants find it hard to understand 1.3; System thinking - The participants suggest that 1.4 is specified a bit more, e.g., what transdisciplinary means in terms of zero pollution)
Proposed competencies	- Better solutions for plastic - Better cleaner energy and technological improvements - Waste and improving waste management
Most important competencies	- The participants point to the importance of these competencies: - 1.1, 1.2 - 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9

GREEN BUILDINGS	
General impression	- The participants find the competencies relevant. - The participants find 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 difficult to understand in the context, and ask for clarification.
Proposed competencies	- AI – to regulate consumption of electronics - Hydrogen plant - New technologies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated new and old buildings - Change the part - New materials
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the 2.1, 3.1, 3.2, and 4.3 the most important to learn.

CLEAN ENERGY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant, and positively point out that it touches upon both personal and societal engagement, as well as both economy and strategy. - They point out that 1.3 Collaboration is a broad concept, and that they have not heard of 1.2 system thinking before.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Something regarding availability in the remote locations, - The participants want to learn about how to choose profitable energies, depending on the place you live. - They want to learn about the mistakes of the system we live in, and have a ethical consumption/production mentality. -
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible consumption and production are particularly important as it avoid waste, which is one of the biggest issues.

CLIMATE CHANGE	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find most of the competencies relevant but find it too complicated to understand the competencies. - They point out that some of the competencies are too general, e.g., 3.1, 4.2. - They point out that some of the competencies are too complicated or unclear, e.g., 6.2, 7.1. - They point out that some seem repetitive and could be simplified into one point, e.g., 4.1 and 4.2. And 2.2, and 3.1.
Proposed competencies/Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do we make just adaptation and handle the different catastrophes related to climate change? - Who will pay, the people it hit or the people who create the problem? (E.g., Should the global north pay for the damage from floodings in Sudan and Pakistan?) - How should vulnerable areas be protected? (Often poor places in the world, who will pay for the protection) - Should there be a global price on co2 emissions, where the money will go to adaptation and rebuilding? - How do we inform people in the global south about climate change? - How do we transform the knowledge we have on climate change into action? - Should we spend a lot of time adapting to the changing climate, or should we try to stop it from changing?

FROM FARM TO FORK	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the theme particularly important in the green transition and find that it is an effective way that consumers/lay citizens can influence the green transition, if they have the knowledge. - They find the subject hard to understand if they have not studied before. - They suggest that some of the competencies are a bit unclear, e.g., 2.2. - They find that 3.3 and 1.3 could be merged into one and presented more precisely put together. - They find 1.2 complicated to understand.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water irrigation - Promotion of local products to increase the local economy - They ask for a focus on the difference between developed and underdeveloped countries – for instance regarding the privileges that citizens in developed countries have.

Connections between competencies:

Reference: [Mural YA4](#)

Part 3: Appearance on the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page

The participants individually explored the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page and answered yes/no questions, guiding them to get an overview of the framework.

Questions	Yes	No	Comments
Do you think the background should be black or white?	18 (black)	24 (White)	
Do you like the 'START HERE' page?	28	8	
Do you prefer the table of content on the right side or the left?	20 (left)	20 (right)	

Do you prefer pictures or no pictures?	35	1	
Do you think the explanation of 'competence', 'knowledge', 'skills', and 'attitudes' is clear?	34	6	It could be explained more comprehensibly, to ensure that more people will understand it.
Do you think the explanation of EQF levels is clear?	23	12	
General comments			Some of the participants find the site is a bit overwhelming and ask for a 'light' version. Some participants find the design nice but the instructions are unclear and confusing.

Part 4: Appearance and usability of the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page

The participants explored the GreenSCENT Competence Frameworks' web page in groups of 4-5 participants. They answered questions regarding the Competence Framework, which encouraged the participants to share innovative ideas, questions, and constructive feedback.

What do you think of the clarity of the 'start here' page?	The participants find that the text makes sense, it is easy to navigate, but it could use some improvements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the 'start here' page should be on top of the list in the left navigation panel - Make the title bigger - Make the 'start here' page the front page when the web page opens - More pictures - Less links
If needed, what would improve the explanation of the EQF levels is clear?	Some of the participants find the information well balanced, while others suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain/introduce what EQF level means, and why it is important. - Gather the information on one page, rather than in many. - Use pictures or real-life examples to increase understanding.
If needed, what would improve the explanation of the word 'competence' and 'knowledge', 'skills', and 'attitudes' is clear?	Some of the participants find the explanations meaningful, while other suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use easier words, - Use pictures - Make it clear and simpler.
What do you think of the general usability of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework in Obsidian?	The participants find Obsidian useful, but complicated. They suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More space between the titles, - Better organization of the main contents, e.g., make a drop menu, instead of all the subtitles. - More colors - Less color on the links, e.g., only the number is colored to show it is a link, instead of the number and the words.

<p>What do you think about the additional categories that emerged?</p>	<p>The participants find the emerged categories confusing; they suggest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce the categories or summarize the ideas behind the categories. - Remove the Wikipedia links.
<p>Do you identify relations between the competencies described in the framework? (You can use the octagon to show the relations).</p>	<p>The participants have some suggestions for improvement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It should be easier to read the competencies when you have the mind map open. It should be simplified. - The octagon is helpful for understanding the competencies better. It could be used on the web page. - Add colors.
<p>What can in your opinion improve the competence framework in general?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The web site needs improvement in organization, - Colors and pictures to show connections, and to make it more appealing - Better outlook, more user-friendly and less information.
<p>Other things or thoughts you want to share?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplify and summarize (as described before) - Add a subtopic to describe how the public can use the web page and collaborate with the project - Leave some more space between competencies - Older computers have a problem loading the page.